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DYNAMIC PREDICTIVE QUANTIZATION FOR STAGGERED SAR SYSTEMS: ALGORITHM DESCRIPTION AND EXPERIMENTS WITH REAL SAR DATA

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INTRODUCTION

Future spaceborne satellite SAR systems will implement advanced acquisition modes, featuring, e.g., digital beam forming and multiple polarization channels in order to acquire larger areas on ground without decreasing the spatial resolution [1], [2]. This will imply the recording of large amounts of data to be stored onboard and then downlinked to the ground. The development of effective data reduction strategies is therefore of paramount importance for the design of a suitable system. In this contribution, we consider a hypothetical SAR system operating in staggered SAR mode: a novel acquisition mode which allows for achieving a fine azimuth resolution (in the order of a few meters) on a wide swath covering hundreds of kilometers in range [3]. A real case example of such a system is represented by Tandem-L: a highly innovative future mission proposal from DLR with the goal of monitoring the natural processes of our planet [1].

The principle of staggered SAR foresees the presence of blind ranges (i.e., gaps) along the swath within the acquired raw data, caused by the fact that the instruments is transmitting a pulse while the echo is being received. By opportunely varying the pulse repetition interval (PRI) during the acquisition, the resulting gaps are staggered along the range dimension following a specific spatial pattern which depends on the utilized PRI sequence. The blind ranges will be present in the data, but may be displaced in a more convenient way in order to efficiently recover the missing information [3]. During the design phase, the variable PRI sequence must be properly selected in order to avoid consecutive missing samples along the azimuth and, at the same time, in such a way that a continuous swath width of hundreds of kilometers (i.e., of about 350km) can be achieved by the system. If the correlation among azimuth samples is high enough, an interpolation along the azimuth allows for the retrieval of the missing information in correspondence of the gaps introduced by the blind range. In order to deal with this issue, a novel quantization method named Dynamic Predictive - Block Adaptive Quantization (DP-BAQ) has been recently proposed [4], which exploits the correlation introduced by the antenna pattern in the oversampled azimuth raw data stream to reduce the amount of data to be stored onboard. Simulations of the proposed method have shown that a data volume reduction capability of about 25% for a typical spaceborne Staggered SAR system can be achieved [4].

In this paper, we demonstrate the applicability of DP-BAQ on real data acquired by the Flugzeug-SAR (F-SAR) [5], the airborne SAR sensor from the Microwaves and Radar Institute of DLR, which has been used in multiple contributions and studies for its reliability and flexibility in performing experimental SAR acquisitions and is depicted in Fig. 1. For this study we have exploited an L-band acquisition over the Kaufbeuren region in Southern Germany and we have opportunely simulated a spaceborne staggered SAR acquisition from the experimental airborne acquisition.

Fig. 1. DLR aircraft Dornier Do228-212, with mounted F-SAR antenna carrier

This allowed us to test the performance of the DP-BAQ technique on real SAR data, by comparing the expected results obtained in [4] with the ones observed for a real SAR acquisition.

In the following section an introduction to SAR raw data quantization is presented, followed by the description of the proposed DP-BAQ and by the application on F-SAR data. Finally, conclusions are drawn in the last section of this paper.

QUANTIZATION OF SAR RAW DATA

The raw data acquired by a SAR sensor usually consists of a complex two-dimensional digital matrix, of which each pixel represents the coherent backscatter of the illuminated targets lying within the antenna beamwidth. Due to the SAR system principle, the mutual correlation among neighboring pixels in the raw data domain is usually rather limited, making onboard data compression a challenging task, also given the limited onboard resources.

Currently operative SAR systems, such as TerraSAR-X and TanDEM-X, are typically equipped with Block-Adaptive Quantizers (BAQ), which represent a simple, yet effective data compression method, offering a good trade-off between the signal representation quality, achievable compression ratio and scheme complexity [6], [7].

The principle of BAQ is to group blocks of range samples and properly adapt the decision levels of the quantizer depending on the statistics of each considered block.

BAQ is typically implemented by means of a cartesian quantizer, which separately encodes the real and imaginary parts of the SAR raw data, as the two complex components are statistically independent.

The encoding quality is usually measured through the signal-to-quantization noise ratio (SQNR), defined as

$$\text{SQNR} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^I |x_i|^2}{\sum_{i=1}^I |q_i|^2} \quad (1)$$

where I represent the number of considered samples, x is the received signal before the quantizer and q is the quantization error calculated as $q = s - s_q$, thus the difference between the uncompressed signal s and its quantized version s_q .

It is important to evaluate the SQNR at the end of the SAR processing (i.e. after the range and azimuth compression), in order to coherently estimate the impact of the quantization on the final product.

DYNAMIC PREDICTIVE BLOCK ADAPTIVE QUANTIZATION (DP-BAQ)

With new acquisition principles aiming at covering wider areas at fine resolution, the BAQ may not be sufficient in order to fulfil the strict requirement represented by the onboard data storage capacity and the downlink bottleneck. For this reason, other solutions have to be investigated.

The applicability of linear predictive coding (LPC) for SAR raw data compression has been first discussed in [8] and [9] and then further elaborated in [4] and [10], where such a quantization scheme is applied along the azimuth direction.

The encoding of the difference between the data and its prediction is the core of this concept. This allows for a reduction of the dynamic range of the signal, resulting in a lower amount of required encoding bits, required to achieve a comparable performance of a standard quantizer operating on the full signal dynamic. The prediction is the result of a linear combination of the N preceding samples, with N representing the order of the predictor. The prediction of $s[n]$ from N previous samples, namely $\tilde{s}[n]$, can be expressed as

$$\tilde{s}[n] = \sum_{i=1}^N \beta_i (s[n-i] + e[n-i]), \quad (1)$$

where β_i is the weight assigned to each i -th previous sample and $e[n-i]$ is the quantization error for the i -th preceding sample. The weights are opportunely defined at system design stage as they are related to the autocorrelation characteristics of the signal, depending on the antenna pattern and the selected pulse repetition frequency $PRF = 1/PRI$ [4].

In this case, LPC is applied along the azimuth direction as a non-negligible correlation is exhibited by staggered SAR systems because of the introduced oversampling [3], [4].

Considering (1) as the prediction of one single azimuth sample, the signal to be quantized is the difference between the actual sample value $s[n]$ and its prediction

$$s_d[n] = s[n] - \tilde{s}[n]. \quad (2)$$

The combination between LPC and BAQ is implemented by first considering the difference between an entire range line and its prediction. Afterwards, the result is encoded using a standard BAQ. A block length of 128 samples can be considered as it is the case onboard for the TerraSAR-X and TanDEM-X SAR satellites.

The encoding schemes reported in Fig. 2 represent the BAQ operation embedded in the prediction process for the encoding (Fig. 2(a)) and decoding (Fig. 2(b)) procedures. It is worth mentioning that the encoding and decoding process is fully coherent, as it exploits the quantized difference for the prediction scheme both on board and on ground. In this way, the process can be inverted on-ground in order to reconstruct the initial signal.

Fig. 2. Encoding (a) and decoding (b) schemes for the DP-BAQ.

As already mentioned, a good system candidate for the application of the DP-BAQ quantization scheme is represented by the staggered SAR acquisition mode, thanks to the presence of oversampling among neighboring azimuth samples. It is possible to define the azimuth oversampling factor OVF_a as the ratio of the pulse repetition frequency and the Doppler bandwidth $OVF_a = PRF/B_d$. For staggered SAR systems OVF_a is in the order of 2 or larger.

Another feature of staggered SAR is the introduction of blind ranges, whose positions varies along the range dimension, because of the cyclical change of PRI in transmission. This condition allows for a continuous large swath width over more than hundred kilometers. The location of blind ranges along azimuth is known a priori, before data take commanding, making it possible to adapt the prediction process according to the gap displacements.

As the name suggests, DP-BAQ introduces the possibility of dynamically varying the prediction order: the sample following a gap is encoded through a direct BAQ, thus no prediction is considered; then a 1st order prediction is performed for the following sample and so on. The prediction order is increased for each sample till the designed maximum order N for the system is achieved. In order to properly recover the missing information in the blind range position, DP-BAQ modifies the bit rate for encoding the sample before and the one after a gap position. If we consider a bit rate of N_b bits/sample, the remaining N_b , which are not used for the gap, are exploited for the adjacent samples.

The signal representation performance in the vicinity of the gaps in the interpolated data (i.e., during on-ground SAR processing) is equivalent to the one of the other gap-free portions of the signal [4], thus the finer representation in the gap vicinity allows for a complete recovery of the missing information due to the blind range [11].

The complete DP-BAQ process is depicted in Fig. 4, where both the dynamic prediction order and the variable bitrate are highlighted.

Fig. 3. DP-BAQ quantization scheme in presence of a gap: the prediction process is restarted after the missing samples and the bitrate is increased for the neighboring samples.

F-SAR DATA

The DLR F-SAR airborne SAR sensor has been used in various experimental test campaigns in order to verify and optimize the design of novel SAR technologies and acquisition modes in real world scenarios [15].

The flexibility offered by the platform has been a key element in testing the DP-BAQ, providing highly oversampled data (oversampling factor of about 20) along azimuth.

A variety of SAR antennas are mounted on the F-SAR system, each one operated at a different radar frequency. The system's main characteristics are summarized in Table 1.

For this paper, an L-band SAR acquisition of about 4 Km in range and 9 Km in azimuth over the Kaufbeuren test site in Bavaria, Southern Germany, has been considered. The SAR backscatter map of the imaged area is depicted in Fig. 4. The raw data acquired by the F-SAR sensor is highly oversampled with respect to a typical spaceborne system, mainly because of the lower sensor speed, which allows for a much larger illumination (integration) time of the considered area on ground.

As a comparison with a standard spaceborne system, we define the oversampling factor in azimuth for the considered F-SAR acquisition as:

$$OVF_{a,F-SAR} = \frac{PRF}{B_d} = \frac{2500}{132} = 18.9 \quad (1)$$

In order to properly emulate a spaceborne staggered SAR scenario, we have resampled the acquisition along the azimuth domain in such a way that the resulting correlation between two subsequent samples is equivalent to the one of a spaceborne staggered SAR scenario. A low-pass filtering along the azimuth dimension is also applied in order to remove the high frequency components from the data to avoid aliasing. We have then performed a second resampling to simulate a non-uniform PRI sequence along the azimuth direction. In this last operation we have also included blind ranges according to the specific PRI sequence.

The upper part of Fig. 5 depicts the abovementioned steps to properly emulate the spaceborne scenario.

We have then quantized the data with different methods at various bitrates: BAQ, 1st order DP-BAQ, 2nd order DP-BAQ, 3rd order DP-BAQ and 4th order DP-BAQ. The complete SAR processing has been carried out for each encoded case in order to obtain a set of SAR products at the available bitrates of 2, 3, 4 and 6 bits/sample. The lower part of Fig. 5 depicts the encoding methods and the following SAR image processing.

Finally, the SQNR on the entire scene has been calculated for the whole scene and is reported in Fig. 6, where different curves represent different quantization methods.

Table 1. F-SAR main system parameters.

	X	C	S	L	P
Carrier frequency [GHz]	9.60	5.30	3.25	1.32	0.43
Bandwidth [MHz]	760	384	300	150	50
PRF [kHz]	5	5	5	10	10
Tx Peak Power [kW]	2.5	2.2	2.2	0.9	0.9
δ_{RG} [m]	0.3	0.6	0.75	1.5	2.25
δ_{AZ} [m]	0.2	0.3	0.35	0.4	1.5
Off-Nadir angle [deg]	25° to 60°				
Swath width [km]	0.6 to 6 according to altitude				

Fig. 4. SAR backscatter of the selected F-SAR acquisition over Kaufbeuren in Bavaria, Germany. It is possible to notice the different types of landcover in the scene such as forest, crops, lakes and urban areas.

Fig. 5. Block diagram showing the processing steps taken into consideration for the simulation of a spaceborne staggered SAR acquisition from FSAR data and the consequent quantization analysis. The dashed line represents the uncompressed version of the data which is used as reference in the performance evaluation block.

From the results, one can note that DP-BAQ outperforms standard BAQ, reaching the same encoding quality of the synthetic simulations performed in [4]. The overall data volume reduction is of about 25%, as the DP-BAQ at 3 bits per sample achieves the same SQNR value of the BAQ at 4 bit per sample.

We have then compared these two representative cases in a more detailed analysis, where the SQNR has been calculated for each point of the scene. The result is depicted in Fig. 7 in the form of SQNR map. It is possible to note that they show a similar performance, as expected from the results in Fig. 6. In particular, the SQNR shows the same distribution and it is related to the backscatter level of the imaged scene in a similar way for both cases: pixels showing low backscatter values (e.g., water bodies, asphalt of the airport and bare soil) are associated to lower values of SQNR, while, on the other hand, high-backscatter targets (e.g., forests and urban areas) are encoded with higher accuracy.

Fig. 6. SQNR calculated after the complete SAR processing. Different curves represent different quantization methods and bit rates

Fig. 7. SQNR in dB calculated for the BAQ at 4 bits/sample (a) and for the 4th order DP-BAQ at 3 bits/samples (b)

We have then computed the corresponding SQNR histograms (depicted in Fig. 7(a)) and phase error (depicted in Fig. 7(b)). The latter parameter is computed as single-look phase difference between the compressed SAR image φ_q and the reference uncompressed one φ , i.e., $\Delta\varphi = \varphi - \varphi_q$ [11]. By observing these two representations, it is possible to assess that the prediction process does not introduce any kind of artefact or inconsistency on the final image, making it a valuable choice for a spaceborne interferometric SAR system.

As it can be seen in Fig. 6, a possible improvement could be obtained by the joint combination of DP-BAQ with a backscatter-optimized quantization scheme as the one presented in [12], where the encoding is optimized for a given performance parameter (e.g., phase error or SQNR) by opportunely varying the bitrate depending on the SAR backscatter power.

Fig. 8. SQNR histogram (a) and phase error (b) calculated for both 4th order DP-BAQ at 3bps and for the BAQ at 3 bps derived for the considered F-SAR acquisition over Kaufbeuren, Germany.

CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

In this contribution we applied the recently developed SAR raw data compression method named Dynamic Predictive (DP)-BAQ on an experimental L-band SAR data acquisition of the DLR airborne F-SAR sensor over the Kaufbeuren area, Germany.

The significant oversampling of the raw data allowed us to properly resample the raw data matrix in order to emulate the signal statistics of a spaceborne staggered SAR system. We have then encoded the resulting raw data matrix with the DB-BAQ at different prediction orders and with the state-of-the-art BAQ as reference baseline. After performing the complete SAR processing for each individual case, we have compared the two methods with a dedicated performance analysis.

The obtained results confirm the expected performance of the theoretical simulation presented in [4]. In particular, the 4th order DP-BAQ at 3 bps achieves on average an SQNR which is equivalent to the one of the BAQ at 4 bps. We have also calculated the SQNR map for the two cases as well as the histograms for the SQNR and the phase error. In these representations, we have shown that the prediction process is not introducing any kind of artefact or inconsistencies in the final product.

Our investigations suggest that the DP-BAQ represents a suitable quantization method for onboard data volume reduction for future spaceborne staggered SAR systems, achieving an additional data volume reduction between 20% and 25% with respect to a state-of-the-art BAQ, by maintaining a comparable data quality.

As possible further optimization it is important to remark that the combination with the presented method with a scene dependent bit allocation, as presented in [12] could improve the overall performance.

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